

1 A new scenario for the mass transport deposits west Canary volcanic province

2 Ricardo León¹, Desirée Palomino², Juan-Tomás Vázquez², Teresa Medialdea¹, Luis Somoza¹

3 ¹*Geological Survey of Spain (IGME), Ríos Rosas 23, Madrid, Spain*

4 ²*Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO), Muelle Pesquero s/n, Fuengirola, Málaga, Spain.*

6 ABSTRACT

7 A new temporal history of mass wasting processes for the west of the Canary volcanic
8 province is presented. Its onset has been estimated in the middle-upper Miocene (~13.5±1.2
9 Ma), matching with a critical period of construction for this volcanic province. Seismic
10 profiles show an emplacement longevity (from the Miocene to Quaternary) in multiple
11 events, defined by stacked lobes of debrites, linked to the flank collapses and volcanic
12 avalanches of the volcanic edifices (islands and seamounts). An evolution of pathways and
13 source areas has been detected from east (Miocene) to west (Quaternary); as well as a
14 migration of the activity to the northwest (west of the Canary Islands: eg. El Hierro and La
15 Palma). Six connected branches (I-VI), three of them described for the first time here, of
16 Quaternary seismic units of mass transport deposits (MTDs) have been characterized. The
17 Pleistocene makes up a huge buried MTDs system, until now unknown, pointing a new
18 mass transport sedimentological scenario. Finally, the two southernmost branches (V-VI),
19 up to now unknown, are a mainly buried system of stacked and terraced lobes of debrites
20 sourced mainly from the flank collapses of the volcanic seamounts of the Canary Island
21 Seamount Province, apparently inactive from upper Cretaceous.

22
23 *Keywords: mass transport deposits, debris flow, Canary Islands*

25 1. Introduction

26 Gravitational instabilities affecting oceanic islands are often associated with volcanic
27 eruptions and fast growth of the edifice as it reaches a critical mass and slope (e.g. [McGuire,](#)
28 [1996;](#) [Paris et al., 2017;](#) [Hunt et al., 2018](#)). These processes are inherent to the evolution of
29 oceanic volcanic islands characterized by eruptive periods of rapid construction ([Ancochea et al.,](#)
30 [2004](#)). Submarine landslides sourced in these volcanic islands are among the largest gravity
31 driven processes on Earth ([Moscardelli and Woods, 2016](#)). They commonly start as onshore-
32 offshore rotational slumps and quickly progress to debris avalanche deposits, later evolving to

33 debris flow and turbiditic processes (Canals et al., 2004). In special cases from the Hawaiian
34 Islands, individual slumps on the flanks of the Hawaiian Islands incorporate up to 5,000 km³
35 (e.g. Moore, 1964) and individual turbidite currents can transport >100 km³ of sand and mud
36 from the continental shelf into the deep ocean (Hunt et al., 2013; Talling et al., 2007; Wynn et
37 al., 2000).

38 The Canary volcanic province is a NE-SW 1,350 km-long ridge of volcanic islands and
39 more than 100 seamounts located in front of the Northwest African coast (Fig. 1), of which
40 related gravitational instability events have been intensively studied (Hunt et al., 2013, 2014;
41 Krastel et al., 2001; Masson et al., 2002; Urgeles et al., 2001). Seventy-seven events have been
42 recorded (up to ~22 Ma) proximal to Canary Islands and 127 (up to ~17 Ma) in the Madeira
43 Abyssal Plain (Hunt et al., 2014). Nevertheless, only the recent events have been located and
44 characterized on the Canary Basin (Masson et al., 1998, 2002; Urgeles et al., 2001; Watts and
45 Masson 1995; Wynn et al., 2000), where the largest, named as the Canary Debris Flow (CDF),
46 extends 700 km from the base of El Hierro Island (Masson et al., 1998; 2002). On seismic
47 profiles, these deposits comprise transparent acoustic facies and are interpreted as debrites. These
48 debrites include over-riding rafted hemipelagite units, representing secondary failures of the
49 seafloor, triggered by the debris avalanches at the base of the volcanic islands (Gee et al., 1999;
50 Masson et al. 1998, 2002).

51 These previous works in the study area show only two recent isolated MTDs (Fig. 1):
52 CDF sourced from the base of the El Golfo Debris Avalanche; and the Saharan Debris Flow
53 (SDF) coming from the base of the African margin and El Julan debris avalanche (Gee et al.,
54 1999; Masson et al., 1998, 2002; Urgeles et al., 2001; Wynn et al., 2000).

55 The transport mechanisms and triggers controlling the MTDs between volcanic debris
56 avalanches in the flanks of volcanic islands and abyssal plains are still controversial. In
57 Montserrat and Martinique (Lesser Antilles), debris avalanches generate seafloor sediment
58 failures in landslide propagation mechanisms (Le Friant et al., 2015; Brunet et al., 2016),
59 whereas in Canary Islands, debris avalanches seem to generate debris flow processes at their toe
60 when they emplace (Urgeles et al., 1999; Masson et al., 1998, 2002).

61 This paper shows a new scenario for the sediment transference applicable in the context
62 of global volcanic ocean islands, in which a long-live and multi-event complex system of
63 volcanoclastic debrites are linking the proximal processes on ocean island flanks and the
64 turbidites accumulated in the adjacent basins in a close timing with the volcanism activity.
65 Besides, this system of debrites gives the clue about when is the onset and the location of the
66 different pathways of this volcanic sediment transference.

67 For the case of the Canary Islands, tThis paper shows for the first time the evidence of
68 ancient MTDs in the lower continental slope of the Canary volcanic province, that can be
69 correlated with their related evidences in the Madeira abyssal plain (Hunt et al., 2014), in the
70 flank of islands (Krastel et al., 2001; Masson et al., 1998, 2002; Urgeles et al., 2001) and onshore
71 (Ancochea et al., 2004; Weaver et al., 1998). This paper provides a broader and more complete
72 perspective of the landslide activity western Canary volcanic province and the seafloor area
73 affected, where its boundaries (based on multibeam backscatter and VHR seismic data) largely
74 exceed those defined in previous works due to the newly detected buried MTDs. This paper
75 presents for the first time the onset at $\sim 13.5 \pm 1.2$ Ma of the mass wasting processes both in the
76 Canary Islands Seamount Province (CISP), up to now inactive as volcanoes since upper
77 Cretaceous (van den Bogaard, 2013), and in the active west Canary Islands. This situation draws

78 a new and unknown mass transport scenario for the west Canary volcanic province refining our
79 knowledge of the two last large-volume debris flows west of La Palma and El Hierro islands, as
80 well as highlighting the presence of additional debris flows west of the Canary Islands and
81 additional buried debris flows west of CISP. This newly evidence of ancient buried MTDs
82 between the western Canary volcanic province and the Madeira Abyssal Plain (Fig.1) reveals
83 new sourcing areas, pathways and an extension largely exceeding the Quaternary MTDs
84 published. These huge bodies of MTDs are composed by individual stacked debrites, directly
85 related with the volcanic/tectonic activity, showing a model for replication in other areas of the
86 world for the sediment transference between the debris avalanches in the flanks of the volcanic
87 islands and the abyssal plains throughout a long-live and multi-event of a braided system of
88 stacked lobes of debrites incised by turbidite channels.

89

90 1.1. Terminology

91 In this paper, landslide is used as a general term for any type of slope failure and resulting
92 mass movement (Canals et al., 2004). The term debris avalanche is used for a very rapid
93 downslope flowage of less cohesive rock fragments from volcanic edifices (Masson et al., 2002).
94 Debris flows comprise rapid laminar flows of disaggregated and remolded material with high-
95 sediment concentrations specifically a high-density mudflow containing abundant coarse-grained
96 materials, their deposits are named debrites (Elverhoi et al., 2000). Turbidity currents are diluted
97 sediment in turbulence flows of coarse-grained material and their deposits are named turbidites
98 (Talling et al., 2007).

99

100 2. Methodology

101 The present study is based on a geophysical dataset (Fig. 2c) obtained in ten
102 oceanographic cruises between 1988 and 2013 comprising 440,000 km² of multibeam (MB)
103 echosounder (bathymetry and backscatter) data (Kongsberg-Simrad EM-12, EM-120 and EM-
104 302, and Atlas HYDROSWEEP DS); 65,800 km of very-high resolution (VHR) profiles (chirp
105 parametric source TOPAS PS-18 and Atlas PARASOUND P-35); and 4,896 km of multichannel
106 time-migrated seismic reflection profiles (MCS) acquired with a system of two array of air-guns
107 yielding a total capacity of 6,600 inch³ and with a 3,500 m long Sentinel digital streamer
108 composed of 280 channels. MB echosounder data have been processed using CARIS
109 HIPS&SIPS software, giving bathymetric and backscatter mosaics of 150 m with 100%
110 coverage. After processing, VHR and MCS seismic profiles were imported as SEG-Y files into
111 IHS KINGDOM TM software for interpretation. Interval seismic velocities calculated by
112 [Medialdea et al. \(2017\)](#) have been used. These authors have checked these data with available
113 regional seismic velocity information and are in accordance with those reported in DSDP Sites
114 137-139 ([Hayes et al., 1972](#)).

115

116 **3. Results: a new seism-stratigraphic architecture of MTDs**

117 *3.1. The Miocene MTDs seismic unit*

118 Multichannel seismic profiles reveal for the first time in the study area, a thick buried
119 seismic unit of MTDs sourced from both the Canary Islands and the seamounts of the CISP (Fig.
120 3). The base of these MTDs is at ~350 ms TWT bsf, above an unknown regional erosional
121 unconformity, which we have named “R”. The unit is about 200 ms TWT thick. Below the “R”
122 unconformity, no transparent acoustic facies related to MTDs deposits are observed. Besides,
123 sediments appear affected by sub-vertical faults and smoothly folded.

124 We date the base and the top of these multi-event MTDs at the middle-upper Miocene
125 ($\sim 13.5 \pm 1.2$ Ma) and upper Miocene (6.2 ± 0.5 Ma), respectively, assuming an interval seismic
126 velocity of $1,940 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ TWT, derived from stacking velocities (Medialdea et al., 2017), and an
127 average sedimentation rate from ~ 1.8 to $\sim 2.8 \text{ cm ky}^{-1}$ weighted following Firth et al., (1996):
128 $\sim 2.3 \text{ cm ky}^{-1}$ for the first 30 m, $\sim 1.8 \text{ cm ky}^{-1}$ for the next 30 m and $\sim 2.8 \text{ cm ky}^{-1}$ for the rest (Fig.
129 2b).

130 Below “R” unconformity, several and different unconformities without massive MTD’s
131 have been observed between the north (Fig. 3b) and the south (Fig. 3c) of the study area,
132 separating two seismic units. The lower is characterized by an alternation of high and low
133 amplitude reflections, well stratified and with a semi-transparent general aspect and down-lap to
134 the basin. The upper has a strong erosive character at the top and is defined by semi-parallel
135 continuous reflections of high amplitude. This unit decrease in thickness to the Echo seamount.

136 Above “R” unconformity, seismic levels of transparent acoustic facies appear stacked,
137 reaching the seafloor, separated by continuous reflections of high amplitude of limited lateral
138 extension (colored in Figs 3b and 3c). Two groups of transparent acoustic facies can be
139 observed. One group is located closed to the base of slope of islands and seamounts representing
140 thick (ca. 200-300 ms TWT), homogeneous, high reflective and transparent acoustic bodies of
141 around 30-40 km in extension in the seismic profiles. The base of these bodies lies over high
142 amplitude and continuous reflectors while the top is irregular often with huge blocks (Fig. 3b).
143 At the end of this group, starts the second group of transparent acoustic facies. This group forms
144 interbedded bodies of transparent acoustic facies separated by high amplitude and continuous
145 reflectors that extends more than 300 km western Echo seamount (Figs. 2 and 3). Internally it

146 configures stored and imbricated wedges of transparent acoustic facies of ca. 100 ms TWT in
147 thickness and 30-70 km of lateral extension measured in the MCS seismic profiles.

148

149 *3.2. The Quaternary MTDs seismic unit*

150 Based on VHR seismic profiles and backscatter mosaics, the upper sequence of MTDs
151 has been characterized. Six connected branches have been defined (I-VI; [Fig 4](#)), three of them
152 described for the first time here. They make up a huge, previously unknown, buried seismic unit,
153 of debrites that extend more than 200,000 km² from the base of the western flanks of La Palma
154 and El Hierro islands and the southernmost seamounts (e.g. The Paps, Echo, Tropic) to the
155 Madeira Abyssal Plain and possibly the north of the Cap Verde deep basin ([Fig. 4](#)).

156 The internal architecture of the upper sequence of MTDs has been re-defined. VHR
157 seismic and backscatter mosaic reflect a complex braided pattern of stacked lobate deposits of
158 transparent acoustic character ([Figs. 5 and 6](#)). Each lobe is separated by high amplitude
159 reflections. The spatial distribution of these debrite lobes appears at least partly related to the
160 WNW-ESE-oriented oceanic fractures zones ([Figs. 3 and 7](#)).

161 *3.2.1. Northern system*

162 Branches I and II form a bifurcate set of debrites. Only, the more recent event of these
163 branches are correlated with CDF defined by [Masson \(1996\)](#). VHR seismic profiles show that
164 these branches have a common buried body of stacked debrites sourced from both La Palma and
165 El Hierro islands. In the distal area, this buried debrites largely exceed the boundaries of the CDF
166 with 190 km in width.

167 Branch I has 350 km of runout and is bifurcated into two main lobes ([Fig. 4](#)), and branch
168 II has 750 km of runout and a variable width ranging from 92 km in the proximal area to 15 km

169 in the distal area. Both branches (I and II) appear on the backscatter mosaic as a NW-SE
170 elongated complex braided system of lobes of debrites with contrasted (high) backscatter
171 strength respect the surrounded seafloor (moderate-low) (Fig. 5). The debris flow bodies are
172 braided together (stacked and intertwined; Figs. 5 and 6) and show a homogeneous high
173 backscatter character. Some of them show a moderate backscatter value with an intertwined
174 textural character is marked by a superimposed net of small turbidite braided channels of 1.5 –
175 5.5 m depth. There is another secondary net of bigger turbidite channels eroding this braided
176 system of lobes of debrites. In the proximal area, these channels are 13 – 20 depth and 1.5 – 3
177 km width, some of them up to 8 km in width (Fig. 6b). Downslope, the braided erosive turbidite
178 channels reach up to 300 km in length and 50-70 m deep (Fig 6a). The distal area of branch II is
179 transformed into a ramified debrites system bounded by narrow (~1 km width and ~25 m deep)
180 turbidity channels, that produced debrites along structural stepped terraces (Fig. 5a).

181 Branches I and II are composed of stacked debrite lobes of 5-12 ms TWT thickness, in
182 the edge of the branch stacked vertically above one-another, and in the lateral as individual sets
183 of debrites separated by continuous reflections at different burial depths such as 12-15, 20-25, 40-
184 57 and 65 ms TWT below seafloor (bsf). They are characterized by transparent seismic facies
185 (Fig. 6) with local features interpreted as fluid escape structures (Fig. 6a). The penetration of the
186 VHR seismic profiles does not allow the identification of the base of the buried debris flows in
187 some areas.

188 Branch III, described for the first time here, is a narrow and E-W elongate body of
189 debrites with high backscatter values (Fig. 4b). In the proximal area, lobes of debrites infill
190 erosive channels (Figs. 3a and 5b) that are eroding branch II. These main channels (Fig. 3a) and
191 surficial debrites seem to be sourced from the base of the El Julian DA.

192 The distal area shows two parts; one over seafloor with a positive relief and onlap
193 relationship, and a second buried below ~10 ms TWT at the last half part.

194 Branch IV (400 km long and 50 km wide) is composed of W-E stacked debrites with high
195 seafloor backscatter (Fig. 4b). The data correlate the SDF with the most recent debrites of this
196 branch (Gee et al, 1999). VHR seismic profiles display a complex set of lobes of positive relief
197 (Figs 3a, 5b and 7a) organized in the edge by vertically stacked one-another and intertwined
198 together. At least 5 imbricated events of 7-10 ms TWT in thickness of elongated lobes of
199 debrites have been detected, both in the distal and central areas (Fig. 7a). The central axis of the
200 branch is occupied by a deposit of ~18 ms TWT in thickness. In the lateral areas (north and
201 south) a buried debrite at 7-10 ms TWT bsf has been characterized (Fig. 7a). Debrites overly a
202 complex seabed morphology affected by smooth folds and subvertical faults.

203 Thin fan-shaped lobes (FSL) are deposits of medium-high reflective seafloor character
204 and 3-5 ms TWT in thickness (Figs. 4, 6a and 7a). They are well developed in the northern
205 system and related to the branches I and II with turbidite deposits (Weaver et al., 1992, 2000;
206 Wynn et al., 2000; Stevenson et al., 2012). In this area, FSL are mainly located in the distal area
207 of these braches (Fig.6a) at the end of narrow and steep wall turbidite channels (Figs. 5 and 6).
208 Frequently, the narrow channels are related with increasing seafloor slope gradient (profiles 1
209 and 2 in Fig. 5a). Sometimes these narrow turbidite channels start at the distal parts of FSL
210 connecting another FSL seaward (Fig. 5a).

211 This study reports for the first time, FSL linked to branches III and IV coming from La
212 Palma and El Hierro islands (Fig. 4 and fsl in Fig. 7). Unlike for the branches I and II, narrow
213 and steep wall turbidite channels are absent and FSL are located over open turbidite channels of
214 smooth profile comprising thin lobes of positive relief and contrasting backscatter acoustic

215 facies. These lobes show a more elongated fan-shaped morphology than in the northern sector,
216 and are located at the end and over-topping braided turbidite channels. In branch III, FSL are
217 terraced and located on both sides, having overflowed the braided turbidite channels sourced
218 from El Hierro Island. In branch IV, FSL are channelized and located in the distal area, defining
219 at least four lobes that are 3-5 km wide and 25-78 km long (fsl in Fig. 7a).

220

221 3.2.2. *Southern system*

222 The southern system, branches V and VI, is described for the first time in the study area
223 (Fig. 7b). It extends 400 km westwards of the southernmost seamounts of the CISP (Fig. 4), with
224 a NW direction. Although local recent debrites have been observed in the eastern flank of Echo
225 Seamount and in the northern flank of The Paps (Fig. 4), the southern system is a mainly buried
226 system.

227 The headers of branches V and VI have not been completely determined. Nevertheless,
228 the main source of the branch V seems to be located in the western flanks of Echo seamount and
229 San Borondón crest (a NNW-SSE elongated seafloor smooth elevation between Echo and Tropic
230 seamounts; Fig. 4). To the east of these seamounts lobes of buried debrites are very scarce. On
231 the other hand, between The Paps and Echo seamounts is where stacked lobes of buried debrites
232 reach the maximum representation and thickness (175 ms TWT). Around The Paps seamount the
233 branch V extend 30-60 km and are practically not present to the north of Ico seamount.
234 Nevertheless, southern Ico and The Paps seamounts and western Drago seamount and San
235 Borondón crest, the branch V constitutes a long (400 km) complex of buried debrites at depths of
236 8, 10-11 and 15-21 ms TWT bsf with a width highly variable between 175 and 50 km, in the
237 proximal and distal areas, respectively (Fig. 4). The debrites of the branch V compose

238 continuous and elongated bodies (100-200 km long) of transparent acoustic facies and ca. 35 ms
239 TWT thick, located over the branch VI profiting negative relieves (Fig. 7b).

240 The header of branch VI is undetermined located to the east of CISP and extends ca. 340
241 km north-western to Tropic seamount. Southern flanks of Drago seamount and San Borondón
242 crest seem to be the northern boundaries of this branch. Branch VI forms stepped and imbricated
243 lobes of debrites showing transparent acoustic seismic facies of VHR seismic profiles with at
244 least 300 km in width. This branch is overlying a highly deformed substrate by both faults and
245 folds profiting the negative relieves for its deposition. On the contrary of branch V, their lobes of
246 debrites do not present so much lateral continuity, showing a lenticular structure due to the
247 stepped substrate.

248

249 3.2.3. *Age of the buried seismic unit*

250 According to the average seismic velocities of 1550-1600 ms⁻¹ and the sedimentation
251 rates (~2.3 cm ky⁻¹) reported in the ODP Site 958A (Firth et al., 1996), we have estimated an age
252 of 243-347 ka and 417-521 ka for the top of the buried debrites at 7-10 ms (branches III-IV) and
253 12-15 ms (branches I-II) TWT bsf, respectively (middle Pleistocene). In the southern branches
254 (V-VI), the top of the deposits at 8-11 ms TWT bsf to the north of The Paps seamount have been
255 estimated at 278-382 ka; and the deeper at 15-21 ms TWT bsf at 521-729 ka (middle
256 Pleistocene).

257

258 4. Discussion

259 4.1. *The onset of the MTDs west Canary volcanic province. A critical period of construction*
260 *of the Canary Islands*

261 The lack of MTDs below the “R” unconformity and the presence of a thick package of
262 Miocene MTDs above this surface, suggests that the onset of the gravitational breakdown of the
263 western Canary volcanic province took place in the middle Miocene. In this way, [Hunt et al.](#)
264 [\(2014\)](#) shows the timing to larger-volume (50-150 km³) turbidites in the Madeira Abyssal Plain
265 that relate to progressive mass wasting in the Western Canary Islands from ~7 Ma to recent.

266 This onset of gravity failure of the Canary volcanic province is contemporaneous with: (i)
267 the oldest collapses detected onshore in the south of Gran Canaria (Fataga 9-11.5 Ma) and La
268 Gomera (~12 Ma) islands ([Ancochea et al., 2004](#); [Weaver et al., 1998](#)); and (ii) the “JA”, “IZ”,
269 “13-19” volcanoclastic turbidites (~12-~10.5 Ma; [Hunt et al., 2014](#)) in the Madeira Abyssal
270 Plain.

271 The inception of volcanic islands represents the largest emplacement of MTDs on the
272 seafloor during the island life cycle. These older MTDs may reflect failures during island growth
273 e.g. Gran Canaria or Tenerife, with a conflation of both subaerial and submarine collapses ([Hunt](#)
274 [and Jarvis 2017](#)). The base of the Miocene seismic unit of MTDs, “R” unconformity, is
275 contemporaneous with a critical period of construction of the Canary Islands and seamounts, the
276 main growth phase of the basal oceanic units in the eastern and central Canary Islands (e.g.
277 Gomera, Tenerife and Gran Canaria, during the middle-upper Miocene; [Ancochea et al., 2004](#);
278 [van den Bogaard, 2013](#)). During this long period, multi-phases of volcanic growth on multiple
279 islands and possibly seamounts ([Hunt and Jarvis 2017](#)) took place that could result the observed
280 thick unit of MTDs.

281 The ages estimated for the buried debrites in the branches III-IV (243-347 ka) and
282 branches I-II (417-521 ka), match with those proposed for the debris avalanches of El Hierro
283 (Las Playas, El Julan: 176-500 ka) and La Palma (Cumbre Nueva; ~520 ka) ([Masson et al., 2002](#);

284 [Urgeles et al., 2001](#)). Besides, these above buried debrites of branches I-II could be related with
285 the “N” (~490 ka) and “P” (540 ka) volcanoclastic turbidites in the Madeira Abyssal Plain
286 sourced from the La Palma and El Hierro islands, respectively ([Hunt et al., 2013](#)).

287 While branches III-IV show a frequent activity from middle-upper Miocene to present,
288 branches V-VI only show intensively activity until the Pleistocene and latent until recent with
289 local and small instabilities on the flanks of CISP seamounts ([Palomino et al., 2016](#)). In this
290 sense, although the seamounts of the CISP have been volcanic inactive since approximately the
291 upper Cretaceous ([van den Bogaard, 2013](#)), MTDs sourced from this region suggest a volcanic or
292 tectonic re-activation during the Neogene and Quaternary. This fact is supported by the tectonic
293 features (faults and folds) detected on seismic profiles ([Figs. 3 and 7](#)); and/or the cone-shaped
294 positive relieves located over Echo seamounts that could be related to possible later volcanic
295 activity. Besides, levels with volcanic glasses have been detected in the Subunit IA – Pleistocene
296 ([Figs 2a and 2b](#)), as well as Quaternary hydrothermal and volcanic activity has been detected in
297 the Subvent area ([Fig. 1](#)) of the deep Canary Basin ([Medialdea et al., 2017](#)) coincident in part
298 with the working area presented here.

299

300 *4.2. A new frame for the MTDs sourcing areas*

301 Three main origins could be established to justify the presence of MTDs or
302 volcanoclastic deposits with blanking acoustic facies between volcanic debris avalanches in the
303 flanks of volcanic islands and abyssal plains: (i) seafloor sediment failures and landslide
304 propagation mechanisms triggered by volcanic flank-collapse events (eg. as in Montserrat and
305 Martinique, Lesser Antilles; [Le Friant et al., 2015](#); [Brunet et al., 2016](#)); (ii) volcanoclastic debris
306 flow triggered by the loading of the slope sediments by the debris avalanches ([Urgeles et al.,](#)

307 1999; Masson et al., 1998, 2002); (iii) pyroclastic density currents (Somoza et al., 2017;
308 Trofimovs et al., 2008). These three options are related with active volcanic periods. Pyroclastic
309 density currents have been identified only in the flanks and base of volcanic island (Somoza et
310 al., 2017), and local possible submarine slide deposits have been interpreted at the base of the El
311 Golfo DA (SLB in Fig 3a), both related with the increase of the volcanic activity. In this way, the
312 most plausible scenario for the volcanoclastic debrites could be the loading of the slope
313 sediments by the debris avalanches (Urgeles et al., 1999; Masson et al., 1998, 2002), related with
314 the volcanic activity too. The extension and shape of the branches I-IV (700 km long x 100 km
315 wide), as well as its internal structure by stacked buried debrites, differs with the SLD published
316 by Brunet et al. (2016) and Le Friant et al (2015). Finally, pyroclastic density currents, maybe
317 triggered by gravitational instabilities, could be a possibility of alternative sedimentary
318 mechanism, since they could be channelized along the turbidite channels of the braided system
319 and reach deeper areas. On the contrary, we have no evidences of pyroclastic density currents
320 beyond the base of the islands.

321 Based on the VHR seismic data the Quaternary seismic unit has been re-defined. The
322 most recent multi-event of debrites related to the branches I and II has been correlated to CDF
323 defined by Masson et al., (1998). According these authors, these debrites came from El Golfo
324 Debris Avalanche (DA). Nevertheless, VHR seismic profiles show that the branches I and II
325 have an extensive common buried body sourced from both La Palma (Cumbre Vieja/Playa de La
326 Veta DA) and El Hierro islands (El Golfo DA). These observations will imply that maybe more
327 variables and sourcing areas will take place in the evolution of the current configuration of CDF.

328 The newly branch III described in this paper and until now unknown, pointing out that the
329 sourcing area of El Julan DA (El Hierro island) has been a bigger impact in the evolution and

330 configuration of the Canary continental slope than was imagined in previous works that only
331 pointing out a local sediment contribution to the SDF. In this way and as above mentioned, the
332 estimated age for the branch III mostly buried (only a ~25% of its extension is over seafloor) at
333 12-15 ms TWT (243-347 ka) match with the age proposed by El Julan DA of 176-500 ka
334 (Masson et al., 2002). This decreasing in the activity of the branch III seems to be observed in
335 the Madeira Abyssal Plain as a lack of records. The last volcanoclastic turbidites correlated to El
336 Julan slide are dated at ~520-540 ka (beds "P" and AP"; Hunt et al., 2014) and no other El Julan
337 slide-sourced landslides seem to be large enough to form a turbidite in the Madeira Abyssal Plain
338 later.

339 In the northern system, FSL have been related to several branches. The FSL located in
340 the branches I and II, have been related to turbidite flows of a braided turbidite system belonging
341 to the Madeira Distributary Channel System (Masson 1994; Stevenson et al., 2013; Talling et al.,
342 2007). We argued that the induced flow pathways of the FSL are pointing out to a broad source
343 area related to gravitational instability and/or volcanoclastic flows coming from both (i) west of
344 La Palma island, (ii) the northern flank of the Tenerife Island, and (iii) the continental margin
345 that matches with the proposed by other authors (Cantagrel et al., 1999; Hunt et al., 2014;
346 Stevenson et al., 2013; Wynn et al., 2000). The FSL related to the branch III, we propose the El
347 Hierro Island as possible main source. For the FSL located at the end of the branch IV (possibly
348 related with debrite deposits), although it has been proposed both El Hierro Island and the
349 continental margin as possible sources (Gee et al., 1999; Wynn et al., 2000), data are pointing
350 out the El Hierro Island as a mainly source and the continental margin as minority.

351 In the southern system, the correlation between branches and sourcing areas has been
352 based on seismic and backscatter data. The branch V shows a great store of lobes of debrites and

353 an increase in thickness to the west of Echo seamount and San Borondón crest. Although an
354 uncertainty amount of sediment coming from the continental margin could be present in this
355 branch, VHR seismic profiles are pointing out to a majority presence of Echo, Tha Paps, Drago
356 seamount and San Borodón crest as sourcing areas. The boundaries of the branch VI have not
357 been defined neither to the East nor and South. Seismic profiles reveal that the presence of
358 debrites coming the seamounts of CISP to the west of Tropic seamount is clear. The landslide
359 palaeo-scars detected in the eastern flanks of Tropic seamount can hardly explained the volume
360 of debrites present to the east of the Tropic seamount. Nevertheless, the ODP Site 958A (Firth et
361 al., 1996) located to the east of the Tropic seamount (Figs. 1 and 2) reveals layers of volcanic
362 clast in the Pleistocene coming the seamounts of CISP. In this way and as in the case of the
363 branch V, we argue a double sourcing areas for the branch V, seamounts of CISP and continental
364 margin, where the participation of the last must be greater.

365

366 During middle-upper Miocene, Las Hijas seamounts (142 Ma) and El Hierro Ridge (133
367 Ma) (van den Bogaard, 2013) were present already in the study area. Neither had La Palma nor
368 El Hierro islands grown above seafloor. This configuration probably allows that the Miocene
369 MTDs sourced further east than the Pleistocene MTDs, from eastern Canary islands, and
370 extended directly downslope to the west. The MTDs coming from the north of Gran Canaria,
371 Fuerteventura and Lanzarote islands (~17-14 Ma; Hunt et al, 2014) were not recorded in the
372 study area, because they possibly followed a northernmost route to the Madeira Abyssal Plain.

373

374 Finally, in several works reported to the west of the Canary volcanic province, MTDs on
375 the island flanks and abyssal plains show a multi-event character of long-lived discrete landslides

376 from the middle-upper Miocene to Quaternary. This multi-event character is supported by the
377 type of failure on the flanks of volcanic islands (Ablay and Hurlimann 2000; Hunt et al., 2011;
378 León et al., 2016) and the information provided by ODP 950, 951 and 952 in the Madeira
379 Abyssal Plain, where 127 (from ~17 Ma to 0) volcanoclastic turbidites emanating from Canary
380 Islands have been distinguished (Hunt et al, 2013, 2018). The new MTDs exposed in this paper
381 are a new evidence of this multi-event and long-lived character (by multiple stacked lobes of
382 debrites at different burial depths in the six defined branches) between the islands/seamounts and
383 the abyssal plains, and reveal for the first time: (i) the big contribution of MDTs sourced from
384 CISP to the abyssal plains; and (ii) at about 13.5 Ma, the start of a west pathway for the main
385 MDTs sourced from the west and south Canary Islands. These above evidences reveal a critic
386 change about 13.5 Ma in the mass wasting transference to the west of Canary volcanic province
387 (Fig. 8). We argue that the multiple construction processes related to the hotspot Canary volcanic
388 province, could explain the long-lived and multi-event character the mass wasting processes (and
389 related MTDs) in this area.

390

391 *4.3. Role of tectonics*

392 MCS and VHS profiles show a folded sedimentary column and faults affecting the
393 seafloor that are deep rooted in the acoustic basement. MTDs occupy the concave seafloor areas
394 of this deformed substrate. In this way, faults and folds seem to control the spatial distribution of
395 MTDs (Figs 3, 4 and 7). Besides, a system of WNW-ESE faults (oceanic fracture zones in Fig.
396 1) delineated by magnetic anomalies offsets (Ranero and Banda 1997) affecting the oceanic
397 basement seem to control the direction of branches II and III. In the branch II, it seems to be
398 more evident because these faults (Figs. 3b and 7) limit a basement high to the north, changing

399 the direction of the branch and controlling the deposition of its MTDs to the south of this feature
400 in steeped terraces. Besides, the FSL and turbidite channels are controlled by changes in the
401 seafloor slope gradient (profiles 1 and 2 in Fig. 5a) generated by the tectonic activity (Fig. 7).
402 Quaternary hydrothermal-volcanic activity has been evidenced in the central part of the area
403 presented in this paper (Medialdea et al., 2017) between the branches IV and V. This activity has
404 produced several mounds and a main smooth bulge on the seafloor (Sánchez-Guillamón et al.,
405 2018) that they have probably acted as a barrier to the development of these two branches, and
406 evidence again the role of volcanic activity and the associated deformations with the distribution
407 of these large bodies in the Canary Basin. The areas where seafloor slope gradient increases,
408 change the turbidity current behavior from deposition to efficient bypass of their sediment loads
409 downslope (Stevenson et al., 2013). These areas of higher seafloor slope gradient and the header
410 of turbidity channels are NW-SE aligned and match with the main tectonic features (Fig. 5a). We
411 argue that the slightly terraced profile of the Canary basin could promote the long runout of these
412 MTDs by the successive acceleration of the turbidity flows in the steeper slopes areas.

413

414 5. Conclusions

415 A giant buried complex sequence ($>200,000 \text{ km}^2$) of stacked lobes of debrites west of the
416 Canary volcanic province is recognized for the first time that corresponds with the oldest events
417 of the CDF (Masson et al., 1998) and Sahara DF (Gee et al., 1999) previously described.

418 The base of this complex sequence of MTDs is located over a regional “R” unconformity
419 (at $\sim 350 \text{ ms TWT bsf}$) dated as middle-upper Miocene. We propose that this unconformity
420 marks the onset of the gravitational breakdown in the western Canary volcanic province and
421 matches with a critical period of construction of the Canary Islands.

422 The MTDs above the “R” unconformity were emplaced over a long period (middle-upper
423 Miocene-Quaternary) in multiple events possibly related with the complex history of growth and
424 collapse of the volcanic edifices. The top of the buried MTDs has been estimated as middle
425 Pleistocene.

426 Six branches (I-VI) have been recognized and their geographical distribution show a
427 morphostructural control and requires re-interpretation of the source areas: La Palma and El
428 Hierro islands for the northern I, II and III MTDs branches; a significant component from the
429 southwestern Canary Islands and to a lesser extent from the African margin for branch IV; and
430 mainly the CISP for the southern (V-VI) MTDs.

431 The proposed methodology and sedimentary transference frame should be applicable, in
432 the context of global volcanic ocean islands, to define onset and pathways of this sedimentary
433 transference in a long-live and multi-event scope, as a geological link between the flanks
434 evolution in volcanic ocean islands (construction/destruction) and turbidites accumulated in
435 adjacent basins.

436

437 **Acknowledgments**

438 We thank James Hunt, David Mosher and Sara Lafuerza for thorough reviews and clever
439 suggestions which helped to improve the article. This work has been supported by the Spanish
440 research project SUBVENT (CGL2012-39524-C02) and the project for the Extension of the
441 Continental Shelf West to Canary Islands (CTM2010-09496-E).

442

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547

548 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

549 **Figure 1.** Geological schema of the mass transport deposits (MTDs) published in the
550 Canary volcanic province (modified from [Masson, 1996](#); [Urgeles et al., 1997](#); [Masson et al.,](#)
551 [1998, 2002](#); [Wynn et al., 2000, 2002](#); [Gee et al., 1999](#); [Krastel et al., 2001](#); [Wynn and Masson](#)
552 [2003](#); [Acosta et al., 2002a, 2002b](#); [Talling et al., 2007](#); [Georgiopoulou et al., 2009](#); [Hunt et al.,](#)
553 [2011, 2013, 2014](#)). Red dash line: contribution of the present paper to Quaternary MTDs
554 mapping based on VHR seismic profiles, bathymetry and backscatter data. CDF, Canary Debris
555 Flow; SDF, Saharan Debris Flow. Oceanic fracture zones (taken from [Ranero and Banda 1997](#)).
556 A general age progression is observed from the oldest Lars volcanic seamount (68 Ma), to the
557 westernmost La Palma and El Hierro islands, which are both younger than 2 Ma ([Geldmacher et](#)
558 [al., 2005](#); [van den Bogaard, 2013](#)).

559 **Figure 2.** Data and methods. (a) ODP site 958A ([Firth et al., 1996](#)) and correlation with
560 TOPAS profile 20110913192601 of ZEEE2011 cruise. (b) Data from ODP site 958A ([Firth et](#)
561 [al., 1996](#)); lithology, sedimentation rates and geological levels/periods. (c) dataset used in the

562 paper; colored: swath bathymetry coverage. Black lines: high resolution seismic profiles,
563 TOPAS. Red lines: multichannel seismic (MCS) profiles. White lines: location of figures.

564 **Figure 3.** Seismic profiles showing the MTDs to the west of Canary volcanic province.
565 (a) TOPAS profiles of branches III and IV (detail of “B”), location in section B. (b) MCS profile
566 B (CANARIAS88 cruise) to the W of El Hierro, Northern branch. (c) MCS profile GAI-3
567 (GAIRE cruise) to the SW of Echo Seamount, Southern branch. DA, debris avalanche.

568 **Figure 4.** Western Canary MTDs. (a) Mapping of the MTDs and location figures
569 overposted. Oceanic fracture zones from [Ranero and Banda \(1997\)](#). (b) Acoustic backscatter
570 mosaic. Red lines, previous works in the study area (modify from [Wynn et al., 2000](#); [Masson et](#)
571 [al., 2002](#)); yellow lines, present contribution.

572 **Figure 5.** (a) Detail of the backscatter mosaic in the north of the study area, Bathymetric
573 (blue) and slope gradient (purple) profiles (profiles 1 and 2) along turbidite channels. (b) Detail
574 of the backscatter mosaic in the distal area of branch II. (c) Detail of the backscatter mosaic in
575 the proximal area of branches I-IV. White lines, turbidite channels; White arrow, direction of
576 flow; Yellow continuous lines, boundaries of branches; Yellow dot lines, debrite lobes. (d) VHR
577 seismic profile in the distal facies of branch II, TOPAS line TAMU2 20120522074756 of
578 AMULEY cruise. (e) VHR seismic profile in the branches I, II, III and IV, TOPAS lines
579 20110913192601-20110913090725.

580 **Figure 6.** Branch II. Mapping, backscatter details and higher resolution VHR profiles
581 showing the main types of MTDs mapped. (a) Distal facies: TOPAS line AMU21-
582 2012052404045312 of AMULEY cruise. (b) Proximal facies: TOPAS line 26
583 “20131004003254-20131004042938” of MAEC-Subvent cruise.

584 **Figure 7.** (a) Branch IV: Mapping, backscatter details and higher resolution VHR
585 profiles of the TOPAS line 34 “20100814083246-20100814053321” of GAROE cruise. (b)
586 Southern area: branches V-VI: extended and higher resolution VHR profiles of the “TOPAS line
587 AMU62 “20120612025745-20120612091917” of AMULEY cruise.

588 **Figure 8.** Diagram showing the “R” unconformity and main seismic units presented in
589 this work correlated with the events of volcanoclastic turbidites in the Madeira abyssal plain
590 ([Hunt and Jarvis 2017](#)), debris avalanche events in the slopes of the western Canary Islands
591 ([Masson et al., 2002](#)) and the main volcanism episodes in the Canary volcanic province ([van den](#)
592 [Boogard 2013; Hunt and Jarvis 2017](#)).